

Functions of Suffix *-an* in Javanese

Yana Qomariana¹, Ketut Artawa², Agus Subiyanto³

^{1,2}Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Bali, Indonesia

³Faculty of Humanities, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This article aims at describing functions of suffix *-an* in Javanese. Suffix *-an* is the most utilised suffix in Javanese, this suffix is used to create nouns, verbs and adjectives in word formation by maintaining or changing classes of the base. This suffix also functions as marker of reciprocal construction. Data in this article are gathered from novel and magazine which were analysed by using descriptive qualitative method. In the affixation process, suffix *-an* is used solely or together with prefixes and infixes as circumfixes. In several circumfixes, suffix *-an* is attached to reduplicated bases. The analysis also shows that the word formation process that uses suffix *-na* causes vowel shift.

KEYWORDS: word formation, suffix *-an*, derivational, reduplication, Javanese

INTRODUCTION

Javanese is a member of Austronesian Malayo-Polynesia language with approximately 80 million speakers spread in Central and East Java island (glottolog.org). Javanese is spoken in three speech levels, i.e.: *ngoko* 'low', *kromo* 'elevated' and *kromo inggil* 'high'. There are previous studies on Javanese, many of them focused on the speech level (Poedjosoedarmo, 1968; Davies, 2022) and politeness (Norwanto, 2016; Santoso, 2015).

One interesting phenomenon in a language is how new words are formed. Lieber, (2009) identifies several ways of forming words: by borrowing from other languages, compounding two words into one, blending words, clipping parts of a word, reducing a word into its initial letters, conversing one word of a particular word class into other class and utilizing affixes. There are five types of language based on their word formation: 1) analytic language that treats one morpheme as one word; 2) inflecting language where one word contains of several morphemes, 3) incorporating language builds up one complex words out of other words and morphemes, 4) agglutinating language tends to have one to one relationship of morphemes with morphs, and 5) infixing language that inserting vowels in a root that built up of consonants (Katamba, 1993).

Javanese is an agglutinative language with extensive use of affixation. The language employs prefixes, suffixes, infixes and circumfixes in creating words. One of affixes that is used more in Javanese word formation process in suffix *-an*. Almost all word classes in Javanese utilizes suffix *-an* (Poedjosoedarmo et al. 2015: 136). There are studies on morphology of Javanese (Suwadi et al., 1996; Wedhawati et al., 2001; Poedjosoedarmo et al., 2015; Magria & Sari, 2020) which mostly analyzing speech levels and politeness. There is limited discussion on specific function of suffix *-an*. Based on the frequent utilization of this suffix in word formation in Javanese, it is necessary to discuss this suffix on its own. This article is focused on describing functions of this suffix in word formation, specifically on *ngoko* level.

As mentioned above, one way to form a new word is by using affixation. Affixation is the process of attaching affixes to a morphological base (Van Goethem, 2020). Affixes are bound morphemes that need to be attached to a base word. Affixes are categorized into four, namely: i) prefix; ii) suffix; iii) infix; and iv) circumfix. The first type is a morpheme that is attached preceded a base; while the second type is attached to the end of a word. The third type is the infix which is added in the middle of a base and the last kind is circumfix which is a combination of two previous types. Affixation may yield new words of similar word classes or words of different word classes with a new meaning. The class maintaining process is known as inflectional process and the latter is derivational process (Bauer, 2004; Lieber, 2009; Katamba, 1994; Van Goethem, 2020)

Part of affixation is reduplication. Reduplication refers to 'the attachment of a complete or partial copy of the base as a prefix or a suffix' (Geert, 2007:41). Affixation by reduplication is also found in Javanese morphology. Further Geert (2007) divides reduplication into two types and uses Javanese as examples:

- i) Full Reduplication

baita 'ship'	baita-baita 'various ships'
sesupe 'ring'	sesupe-sesupe 'various rings'
omah 'house'	omah-omah 'various houses'

ii) Partial Reduplication

geni 'fire'	gegeni 'to warm oneself by the fire'
jawah 'rain'	jejawah 'to play in the rain'
tamu 'guest'	tetamu 'to visit'

The examples above show that in partial reduplication the prefix contains the first consonant as a copy of the base word which was followed by sound schwa (ə), i.e. *gegeni* is pronounced /gəgəni/ and *jejawah* is pronounced /jəjawah/. The full reduplication contributes meaning of plurality and distributivity.

Affixation in Javanese include prefixes, suffixes, infixes and circumfixes as listed in the following (see Poedjosoedarmo, 2015; Wedhawati et al., 2001; Suwadji et al., 1996):

- i) Prefixes: active prefix N- (with allomorph of : *n-*, *m-*, *ny-*, and *ng-*), *a-*, *ma N-*, *ka-*, *ke-*, *di-*, *sa-*, *mi-*, *pa-*, *mer-*, *pa+N*, *pri-*, *pra-*, *tar-*, *kuma-*, *kami-*, and *kapi-*.
- ii) Infixes: *-um-*, *-in-*, *-el-*, and *-er-*
- iii) Suffixes: *-a*, *-e* (with allomorph of *-ne* and *-ipun*), *-i* (with allomorph of *-ni*), *-an* (with alomorph of *-nan*), *-er*, *-ane*, *-ana*, *-ne*, *-na* and *-ake* (with allomorph of *-ke* and *-aken*).

One previous study on Javanese affixation was written by Magria & Sari (2020). In this research, the writer found prefixes include *ng-*, *di-*, *ben-*, *ke-*, and *ny-*. Another finding in this research is five kinds of suffixes including *-e*, *-ne*, *-an*, *-ane*, and *-en*, and infix that is *-cici-*. This study found a new prefix *ben-* that is attached to nouns to form adverbs. Suffix *-an* was found in the process of :

- i) forming verb from verb, i.e. *bonceng* 'hitchike' *boncengan* 'to hitchike'
- ii) forming noun from verbs, i.e. *goreng* 'fry' *gorengan* 'fries'
- iii) forming noun from noun, i.e. *pitulas* 'seventeen' *pitulasan* 'celebration of the date seventeen/independence day'

This study support information on the function of suffix *-an* functions as the inflectional as well as derivational morpheme.

The next research related to suffix *-an* is a study about derivational and inflectional process in Javanese written by Meyfiany et al. (2024). This research found prefixes *ny-* and *m-* in the process of forming active verbs. Another finding in this research is infix *-um-* to form active noun. The last finding is the use of circumfix suffix *-an* in combination with prefix *pi-* to create a noun from a base verb, e.g. . *takon* 'to ask' → *pitakonan* 'question'. This finding contributes to the word formation process that involves suffix as part of a circumfix.

Another study related to suffix *-an* is conducted by (Nardiati, 1999). In her article, Nardiati analyse suffix *-an* that contains reciprocal meaning. Reciprocal verbs shows these characteristics: 1) two participants with 'identical relationship to each other; 2) both of the participants hold two identical semantic roles, e.g, each participant is agent as well as patient. (Nedjalkov, 2007)

- i) base verb + *-an*
salam 'shake hand' *salaman* 'shake each other hands'
 reduplication of base verb + *-an*. *bkd*
jotos 'hit' *jotos-jotosan* 'hit each other'
- ii) partial reduplication + *-an*
sanding 'next to' *sesandhingan* 'next to each other'
- iii) last syllable of base verb + base verb + *-an*
kemong 'take care of' *mong-kinemong* 'take care of each other'

This research shows suffix *-an* that functions to express reciprocity Javanese.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a descriptive qualitative research by applying observation method and note taking technique. Based on Creswell (1998) this method is suitable for this research as it describes rules about a language which is a social matter in which the date is taken from texts as natural setting. Data in this research are words containing suffix *-an* are collected from a novel entitled *Katresnan*

and *Djaka Lodang* magazine. The data was analyzed by describing the function of suffix *-an* in each sentence and analyzed based on the use of affixes in formation process of each word.

FINCINGS AND DISCUSSION

The data collection shows various function of suffix *-an*, including in the derivation process of forming verbs into nouns or vice versa, the inflectional process of forming passive from active verbs and the formation of reciprocal constructions. These word formation processes are illustrated by the following data:

1a. Aja dolan nyang alun-alun wayah wengi kejaba yen ana pasar malam apa
 Don't visit to square time night unless if there is market night or
 'Don't visit town square at night time unless if there is night market or

tonton-an liya-ne.
 watch- other-DEF
 NMLZ
 other performance.'

b. Kriyet-kriyet soyo cedhak ke-prungu swara-ne salang **pikul-an**
 Kriyet-kriyet more closer PASS-heard sound-DEF between yokes-NMNLZ
 'Kriyet-kriyet the sound of yokes heard closer.'

Two sentences above display formation of noun by attaching suffix *-an*. In sentence no (1a) *tonton* 'watch' is a base verb to which suffix *-an* is added. The addition yields a noun *tontonan* 'performance'. In this process, suffix *-na* functions as nominalizer from verb. The similar process is observed in sentence no (1b) with the base verb *pikul* 'to carry on shoulder'. As there is a change in word class as a result of the affixation, this process is a derivational word formation. Below is the summary of the affixation process:

tonton 'to watch' → tontonan 'performance'
 pikul 'to carry on shoulder' → pikulan 'yokes'

The next sentences illustrate the addition of suffix *-an* that changes noun to verb.

- 2. Kiwa tenge-ne alun-alun dalam **aspal-an** gede.
 Left right-DEF square street aspal-APPL besar
 'Big streets on the left and right of the (town) square are covered by asphalt.'
- 3. Dhewek-e **alem-an**, gelem m-angan ning kudu n-jaluk dulang.
 3PR-DEF spoiled-ADJ willing ACT-eat but must ACT spoon-fed
 'He/she is willing to eat but must be spoon-fed'

In sentence no (2) above, derivational word formation is illustrated by changing a noun into a verb *aspalan*. The change process is summarised as: *aspal* 'asphalt' → *aspalan* 'covered with asphalt.' Suffix *-an* in this sentence also function as applicative morpheme. Applicative is the process of promoting oblique into argument based on the following process:

Dalan kuwi di-tutup-i karo aspal. → Dalan kuwi aspal-an.
 'Street that PASS-covered-APPL with asphalt' 'The street is covered with asphalt.'

Sentence no (3) shows suffix *-an* that is used to form *aleman* 'spoiled' from *alem* 'peaceful':

alem 'peaceful' → *alem-an* 'spoiled'

In this sentence, the base word does not change which is adjective. However, there is a change in meaning from 'peaceful' to 'spoiled', therefore this process is categorised as derivational process.

In the following sentence, suffix *-an* is used with reduplicated base:

4. Latar-e omah-e Yayuk ana pager-e ijo, latar-e amba pager tanduran
Yard-DEF house-DEF Yayuk has fence-DEF green yard-DEF wide fence plant
'The yard of Yayuk's house has green fence, the yard is wide with tea plant as fence of

teh-teh-an t-um-ata rapih.
tea-NMLZ PASS-organize well
a kind of tea organized well.'

In sentence (3) the word *teh* 'tea' is reduplicated before suffix *-an* attached to it. This sentence involves the process of full reduplication. After the addition of suffix *-an* the meaning is given additional meaning which is 'a kind of'. In this sentence, *teh-tehan* means plant that resembles tea.

Nouns can also be formed by reduplicating the beginning part of the word, as illustrated in sentence (5a) and (5b). Only the first consonant of base verb is reduplicated followed by infix *-e-*.

5. a. Lampu-ne **be-bangun-an** anyar lan lawas ny-engsem-ake.
Light-DEF CV-awake-NMLZ new and old ACT-glad-CAUS
'The light of the new and old buildings makes (us) glad.'
b. Isih ana **te-tumpak-an** pating sliwer.
Still there CV-ride-NMLZ all over bustling
'There are still vehicles bustling all over.'

In sentence (5a) and (5b) above the affixation changes the class of base word from verb into noun.

Suffix *-an* can also create circumfix with prefix *pa-* as illustrated in sentences below. In sentence (6a) and (6b) circumfix *pa-an* creates deverbal nouns. In sentence (5a), circumfix *pa-an* is attached to base verb *temu* 'meet' which has undergone vowel alternation and also addition of consonant /n/. One assumption a reason behind vowel alternation is to ease the pronunciation.

- 6 a. Aku ninggal **pa-temo-nan-ku** karo Yayuk.
I left NMLZ-meet-NMLZ=1SG POSS with Yayuk.
'I left my meeting with Yayuk.'
b. Roti tart kuwi wis di-bayar, **pa-ngandikan-e** Ibuk-e Yayuk.
Cake tart DET PERF PASS-paid NMLZ-say=3SG.POSS mother=3SG.POSS Yayuk.
'The tart cake has been paid, said Yayuk's mother.'

Sentences no (6a) and (6b) also demonstrate that noun phrases in Javanese can take possessor which occupy a position at the end of a noun phrase (see Davies & Dresser, 2005).

The following two sentences shows circumfixes that consist of prefix *ka-* which is a passive prefix and suffix *-an*. Function of circumfix *ka-an* is to mark of passive adversative or action that is undesirable (see Nurhayani, 2015).

- 7 a. Roman **k-asmara-n** sing anyar maneh apa wis ana?
Novel PASS-love-PASS that new again what already available?
'Is a new novel about (someone) falling in love available already?'
b. Yen klebon setan bisa gawe ora iling, bisa keladuk **ka-cilaka-n** ing adu asmara.
If possessed evil can make NEGremember can fall NMLZ-unfortunate-NMLZ at collide love
'If possessed by evil it can make (us) forget, (we) can fall in calamity while falling in love.'
c. Ana **ka-nom-an** padha jaga **ka-tentrem-an**.
There NMLZ-young-NMLZ together protect NMLZ-peace-NMLZ
'There are young people protect peace together.'

- d. Wong tuwane korban perlu m-aring-i wewarah marang putra putri-ne kanggo
 Person old-DEF victim need ACT-give-APPL nasihat to son daughter=3PL POSS for
 'Parents need to give advice to their sons and daughter to
- nge-doh-i kahanan sing m-eneh-i **ka-lodhang-an** ombor ana-ne penculik-an.
 ACT-stay away-APPL situation which ACT-give-CAUS NMLZ-opportunity-NMLZ toward
 there-DEFkidnapping
 'stay away of the situation which gives opportunity of the kidnapping.'

In sentence (7a) verb *kasmaran* 'feels in love' is built up from prefix *ka-* that is attached to base noun *asmara* 'love' and suffix *-an*. This affixation process is categorized as derivational because it results in the change of word class from noun to verb. A circumfix *ka-an* also appear in sentence (7b) attached to base adjective *cilaka* 'unfortunate' which form a passive verb *kacilakan* means 'to experience something unfortunate.' In the attachment of prefix *ka-* there is a suppletion process of vowel /a/ as it is added to a base that is started with similar vowel, similar case also occurs to suffix *-an*. Sentence (7c) illustrate the retention of vowel /a/ in suffix *-an*. Sentence (7d) shows the formation of a noun *kalodhangan* 'opportunity' from the base adjective *lodhang* 'space'.

The next sentences display function of suffix *-an* as reciprocal marker. In sentence (8a) suffix *-an* is attached to base verb *salam* 'regards', suffix *-an* contributes the reciprocal meaning to the verb. Sentence (8b) shows suffix *-an* that is used in the second reciprocal construction with reduplicated base verb *omong* 'talk'. Sentence (8c) shows suffix *-an* in the third reciprocal construction that contains infix *-in-*.

8a. Yayuk karo Yoyok **salam-an**.

Yayuk and Yoyok shake-hand-RECP.
 'Yayuk and Yoyok are shaking hand.'

b. Aku lagi wae mingkem **omong-omong-an** karo Kijo ana becak mara.

PRG just finish talk-RECP with Kijo there vehicle come
 'I just finished talking with Kijo when a pedicab came.'

c. Dadi semedulur aku lan Rustam di-anggep kluwarga-ne kaya kapernah adhi,
 Becoming relatives I and Rustam PASS-consider family=3SGPOSS like relative younger
 'Becoming relatives I ad Rustam are considered his family like (his) younger brother'

akrab **tulung-t-in-ulung**.

close help-RECP
 'close help each other.'

The sentences no (8a), (8b) and (8c) meets the criteria for reciprocity. There are two participants in the sentences (8a), they are Yayuk and Yoyok, both of these participants perform the activity of shaking hand to each other. The second criteria is also met as Yayuk is an agent who shakes Yoyok's hand but at the same time, Yayuk is also a patient as her hand is shaken by Yoyok. This also happens to Yoyok. The similar case can be observed in sentence (8b) and (8c).

The addition of suffix *-an* to the verbs in the sentences above create the reciprocal meaning. This can be contrasted to the sentences below in which the verbs do not contain reciprocal meaning:

9a. Aku wis **ng-omong** durung ya

I already ACT-say not yet right
 'Have I said it or not?'

b. Ning aku ana sing **n-ulung-i** njur lulus ujian-e SIM C.

But I have which ACT-help-APPL so pass exam-DEF SIM C.
 'But I have (someone) helped me so I passed SIM C exam.'

The verbs in sentences (9a) and (9b) do not contain suffix *-an* and they are active verbs without reciprocal meaning.

CONCLUSION

This research shows that suffix *-an* is utilized in creating nouns, verbs and adjectives through base changing and maintaining process. Suffix *-an* also forms circumfixes with prefixes and infixes that forms nouns and verbs. One function of the circumfixes is to show reciprocal meaning. In one circumfix that functions as reciprocal marker, suffix *-an* is attached to reduplicated base. Several word formation process using suffix *-an* shows vowel alternation that needs a separated research by itself. This research will show a more comprehensive result with a bigger and more various data.

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